

COMMUNICATION OF PARTICIPATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NGETUN BEACH AS A LEADING TOURIST DESTINATION

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Abstract

Ngetun Beach is an exotic beach because it is located in the niche of Gunung Kidul Hill. However, so far, it has not attracted much attention from tourists. Accessibility to places, travel, and infrastructure is not fulfilled. Even though there is a Pokdarwis, the active participation of the local community is not yet optimal. Research questions about participatory communication developed. Efforts to raise awareness communally through the fantasy of shared welfare and government involvement? Previous research studies on the failure of tourism object management in attracting tourists related to the ecosystem of tourist destinations. The two branding efforts are partial next accessibility and the role of government. However, collective awareness of the importance of tourist destinations has not been studied. Through theory-communication, symbolic convergence from Bormann will be a model for increasing active community participation. This research was conducted using a phenomenological methodology with ethnographic analysis. The study results show that the management of Ngetun Beach is still being approached through a structural approach. The role of the government through regulations is still not optimal. Tourism marketing is done partially, and it still uses a mobilization approach to mobilize community participation. In conclusion, we need to improve participation through active modelling of convergence symbolism. Do integrated marketing and increase the role of the government.

Keywords: Mobilization, Structural, Participation, Government

BACKGROUND

Cultural diversity and topology are seen in the sector of tourism. Lately, Indonesia has even been recognized as superior for several decades. At least by setting ten leading tourist destinations, it shows that tourism potential in Indonesia is a serious concern. However, Lots buffer tourist destinations from leading destinations that cannot be handled in a comprehensive and integrated manner so that they have uniqueness and ease of access.

In setting sector tourism being one superiority in obtaining foreign exchange, the handling of tourism is no longer carried out partially and locally as has been the case so far.

Change of orientation and change management make me more professional in management. In the region of countries such as Malaysia and Vietnam, Singapore has already cleaned up first in packing up tourism well. Even Saudi Arabia has prepared well to become the main source of foreign exchange to replace resource nature.

In Indonesia, various regions that have natural resources as tourist destinations have been tried to be developed, one of which is a tourist destination in the Yogyakarta area. Yogyakarta as the second largest tourist destination after Bali, has many benefits from the branding of a cultural city so that it is widely known by the wider community. Seeing this, the development of destinations is very profitable, such as nature tourism, historical tourism, cultural tourism, educational tourism, and most recently, night tourism. The designation of Yogyakarta as a tourism city illustrates the potential of this province from a tourism perspective to give its own image, which will be able to attract visitors.

Ngetun Beach is one of the beaches in Yogyakarta with beautiful beauty and has different potential from the surrounding beach. Ngetun Beach is located in Purwodadi Village, Tepus District, Regency Gunung Kidul, Province of the Special Region Yogyakarta. The existence of Ngetun Beach in terms of the beach landscape is sufficient to become a reliable tourist destination in Gunung Kidul. The attractive potential is in the form of unspoiled natural beauty, white sand beaches, cleanliness of the clean beach environment, and the shape of the beach flanked by two hills so that this beach looks tiny. Tourists will feel that they are on a private island. This beach also has very good photo spots. On this beach, tourists can also enjoy the beauty of the sunset directly. *Sunset*). On Ngetun Beach, there are lots of fish and lobsters. Because of that, this beach is also a source of livelihood for local people who work as fishermen. Activities that can be carried out by tourists at Ngetun Beach are swimming, fishing, camping and other outbound activities (Zakaria & A'yunin, 2019).

Although Ngetun Beach already has many potential tourism aspects, management as a tourist destination is still being managed with partial steps. Each community group around the beach has to deal with its initiative Alone in attracting tourists to stop at the Ngetun beach tourism area. Awareness of the need for tourists to stop over in the region to improve their well-being in fact there has been, but there has been no shared awareness in dealing with Ngung Beach comprehensively, and there is a lack of promotion about the destination Ngetun Beach.

Tourists who come to visit Ngetun Beach mostly know about it from word of mouth from friends and family, while information via social media as well as websites and brochures is still very rarely a source of information. While the target market for this tourist attraction is suitable for all groups (families, children and adults), it is observed that it is more dominated by adults.

With enormous potential, Ngetun Beach should be a leading beach destination, but deep in fact still inferior to the surrounding beach in terms of tourist visits. This reality leaves questions for further in-depth research on the management approach to Ngetun Beach. This concerns problems that can be seen from the perspective of the development of

interactive communication in the development of shared awareness about the importance of development beach Sorry. So in this study, it can be formulated how participatory communication is developed by managers of coastal tourism areas, sorry? How far can the growth of communal awareness of the beach commodity prosper together? How is the participation of the Government in developing each sorry as a leading tourist destination?

LIBRARY REVIEW

It would be interesting to understand the low number of tourist visits to tourist destinations by looking at various studies on tourism. One of the articles written by Zhu and Deng discusses the factors influencing rural tourism development and the government's role in tourism development Zhu, using empirical studies in China, provides an in-depth analysis of the government's role in developing rural tourism through policies and regulations, support finance, infrastructure development, and tourism promotion, as well as tourism product quality, safety and environment, and cultural and social factors.

In this article, the authors point out that the government plays a very important role in the development of rural tourism and must implement appropriate policies and strategies to enhance tourism competitiveness. This article also makes an important contribution to understanding the key factors influencing the development of rural tourism and the government's role in this regard (Zhu & Deng, 2015). An article entitled "Factors Influencing the Failure of Beach Destination Development in Eastern Region, Peninsular Malaysia" written by Norul Hidayah Abas, Hasbullah Ashari, Siti Rohaida Mohamed Zainal, and Mohd Radzuan Ibrahim, in the journal *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 26, 1-10 Published: 2018 describes the evaluation of the factors that cause failure in the development of coastal tourism destinations in Malaysia, especially in the eastern region of Peninsular Malaysia. Through surveys and interviews with relevant stakeholders, including local government, tourism business actors, and local communities, it was found that factors such as lack of government support and tourism promotion, lack of accessibility and infrastructure, and conflicts between entrepreneurs and local communities were some of the factors that caused failure in the development of coastal tourism. The authors provide recommendations for addressing the problem, such as increasing government support and tourism promotion, developing infrastructure and accessibility, and improving relations between businesses and local communities.

Another article with a quantitative approach entitled "A Preliminary Study on Factors Influencing Local Community Participation in the Development of a Beach Destination in Malaysia" Written by Mohd Hanafi Hanafiah, Rosli Hashim, and AionMardiah Noor, in the *Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Management*, 6(1), 6-14, Year of Publication: 2018 explains the factors that influence the participation of local communities in the development of beach tourism destinations in Malaysia. The research was conducted by interviewing 120 respondents from two villages around Sepat Beach and Kelulut Beach in Malaysia. The results of the study show that factors such as the community's understanding of the economic benefits of the tourism industry, awareness of the need to

maintain the coastal environment, and the active involvement of the government and local entrepreneurs are factors that influence community participation in the development of coastal tourism destinations. The article also provides recommendations for increasing the participation of local communities in the development of coastal tourism destinations, such as increasing public awareness of the economic benefits of the tourism industry, increasing the active involvement of the government and local entrepreneurs, and increasing the skills and knowledge of local communities about the tourism industry.

A study written by Law, Qi, and Buhalis discusses the importance of website evaluation in tourism research. By presenting a comprehensive literature review on website evaluation research in the tourism context and providing a critical analysis of the methodology, results, and contribution of the research. Regarding the importance of developing an effective website in increasing the attractiveness and competitiveness of tourism destinations, it is concluded that the importance of systematic and holistic website evaluation in tourism research (Law et al., 2010).

Several studies on the failure of management of tourist objects in attracting tourists to visit tourist destinations show that there are several factors which influence them. At least in the studies mentioned above, there are four main factors, namely the tourism product factor, which concerns all ecosystems of tourist destinations (Setyaningrum et al., 2022). In this ecosystem, apart from being a tourism object, there is a shared awareness of the importance of tourism objects. Factor the second disintegrate communication activities for branding tourism products. The next factor is accessibility tourism, making it easier for tourists. Factor fourth is the role of the government in providing support for tourism development, specifically tours in the area. Starting from the four main factors for the development of tourism objects, the communication factor plays an important role in building the relationship between tourism object managers and tourism development ecosystems (Arifin & Ardiansyah, 2020).

Public awareness in tourist destinations about the importance of tourism objects requires a symbolic understanding of tourism objects (Harita & Perwirawati, 2021). Herbert Blumer Mead, with symbolic interactional theory, emphasizes the importance of symbols in human interaction and the development of social identity. According to Mead, humans develop an understanding of themselves through social interactions with others, and the symbols used in communication are important tools in this process. To build shared awareness, Mead emphasized that individuals must be able to see themselves from the perspective of others and understand how the symbols used in social interaction affect their identity (Blumer, 1969).

Through a group perspective, Mead's thoughts can be understood through the thoughts of Ernest Bormann, who borrows these ideas to be replicated in the rhetorical actions of society on a broader scale than just small group communication processes. Bormann's researches were intensive throughout the 1970s, which later led to the emergence of the Symbolic Convergence Theory. Bormann, one of his well-known theory is the theory of symbolic convergence which suggests that when different individuals and groups talk

about a problem, they will slowly develop the same views about the problem (Bormann, 1982).

Symbolic convergence theory also explains that with the development of technology and media, people are becoming more connected and exposed to the same symbols and images. This can result in a tendency for social cohesiveness, where people with different backgrounds can feel connected to each other because they are exposed to the same symbols (Oro et al., 2020).

Symbolic convergence theory also states that media and technology play an important role in shaping the symbols and images used in society. In the context of social cohesiveness, the media can help create commonalities and a shared understanding of the values and norms held by society. In building social cohesiveness, symbolic convergence theory emphasizes the importance of media and technology as tools to connect and form the same symbols and images among members of society. Thus, media and technology can help create a sense of unity and solidarity among people of different backgrounds.

In addition to building shared awareness of the community as a tourist destination, another factor is utilizing all the means of disseminating tourism products to build a broad public image of the destination brand. Clow, K. E., & Baack, D in *Integrated advertising, promotion, and marketing Communications* suggests that marketing strategy integrates various different marketing elements, such as advertising, sales promotion, publicity, etc., into a consistent and unified whole. Clow developed the basic concepts in integrated marketing communications concerning several things, namely focusing on consumers. In integrated marketing, consumers are placed at the centre of marketing strategy. All marketing elements are integrated to meet consumer needs and want in a consistent and integrated manner. The concept offered next is message consistency. Each marketing element must have a consistent and unified message to achieve marketing goals effectively. In the use of communication channels, Clow explained that integrated marketing will utilize various communication channels, such as mass media, social media, and e-mail, to reach consumers. Increase in sales, brand awareness, and customer loyalty (Clow & Baack, 2018). By applying the basic concepts of integrated marketing, companies can create continuity and consistency in marketing messages delivered to consumers, increase marketing effectiveness, and achieve set marketing objectives.

In addition to building a fun ecosystem and product marketing strategy for destination tourism, the important role of local government will greatly assist the successful development of tourist areas. The role of government policies in tourism development can shape and direct the direction of national tourism development, increase the competitiveness of tourism destinations at the global level, and provide support and facilitation for tourism actors at the local level. Government policies will greatly influence infrastructure development policies. The government can improve accessibility to tourist areas by building infrastructure such as roads, airports, ports and other means of transportation (Andrianti & Lailam, 2019). For tourism promotion policy, the government can promote Indonesian tourist destinations at the national and international levels

through various media and promotional activities, such as advertisements, tourism exhibitions, and other activities. Regulatory and supervisory policies, the government can ensure the security, safety and quality of tourism services by implementing appropriate regulations and supervising their implementation (Rozi, 2022). In human resource development policies, the government can develop human resources in the tourism sector through training and education so that the workforce available in the tourism sector is of good quality. For sustainable tourism development policy, the government can encourage sustainable tourism development by taking into account environmental, social and economic aspects so that tourism can provide long-term benefits for local communities and the environment. With these policies, it is hoped that the development of tourism in Indonesia can run well and provide maximum benefits for the community and the country (Rakhmadani, 2021).

Philip Kotler, in his book entitled "Marketing for Hospitality and Tourism" (6th Edition). According to him, the government plays a very important role in the development of tourism and has a responsibility to create a conducive environment for the development of a sustainable tourism industry. It goes on to say that the government can play an important role in tourism development by doing the following things:

1. Creating an enabling environment for tourism: Governments should create an enabling environment for tourism development by creating basic infrastructure, promoting tourist destinations, and providing financial and administrative support.
2. Encouraging sustainable tourism development: The government should encourage sustainable tourism development by taking into account environmental, social and economic aspects so that tourism can provide long-term benefits for local communities and the environment.
3. Provide education and training for the workforce in the tourism sector: The government should provide education and training for the workforce in the tourism sector so that they have the necessary skills and knowledge to develop quality tourism.
4. Implement adequate regulations: The government must implement adequate regulations to protect consumers, maintain the quality of tourism services, and ensure security and safety for visitors and local communities (Kotler et al., 2014).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Approach and Method This research uses a qualitative approach with a paradigm objective interpretative. This research was carried out to build knowledge through understanding and discovery of field realities. The qualitative research approach is a process of research and understanding based on methods that investigate a social phenomenon and human problems. This qualitative research approach aims to understand the meaning of human life experiences in their social and cultural context by exploring the views, perceptions, and experiences of the people involved in the phenomenon.

In the research method developed by Edmund Husserl, the researcher seeks to understand the subjective experiences of the people involved in the phenomenon under study and uses methods such as in-depth interviews, participatory observation, and document analysis to collect and analyze data. The researcher then analyzes the data to identify important themes or structures in the subjective experience. In this research, the role of the researcher is as a key instrument in collecting data and interpreting the data. Data collection tools use direct observation, interviews, and document studies. While ensuring the validity and reliability of data using triangulation using inductive methods, the results of qualitative research emphasize meaning rather than generalization.

This research was conducted in the community around Ngetun Beach based on the background that the Ngetun Beach community directly uses the beach as their source of life. They have been utilizing the coast with its natural resources to fulfil their lives so that the economic aspects of the coast and the surrounding sea have become the foundation of their lives. This condition is very interesting to be used as a research area.

Research subjects or informants selected purposely were formal leaders who led village residents and customary informal leaders and community members, as many as three people who represented the older generation and the younger generation as participants. Participants are used, especially if the subject represents a certain group and the relationship between the researcher, and the research subject is considered meaningful to the subject. The researcher, as the main instrument in this study, took concrete steps to go directly into the field for four months by doing the following:

- a) Conducting unstructured observations and interviews, which were deemed more feasible.
- b) Looking for meaning in every behaviour or action of the object of research so that an original understanding of contextual problems and situations is found.
- c) Triangulation, data or information from one party is verified by obtaining information from other sources.
- d) Using an emic perspective means comparing the views of informants in interpreting the world from their own point of view.
- e) Verification, among others, through conflicting cases to obtain more reliable results. The researcher looks for various cases that are different or contradictory to what has been found, with the aim of getting results that are more accurate at the level of confidence and cover a wider range of situations that allow him to combine various cases.
- f) Conduct analysis from the beginning to the end of the study. The intended analysis is to interpret the data obtained as a manifestation that all descriptive methods and descriptions contain interpretations.
- g) Carrying out a phenomenological approach.

The analysis technique uses the analytical concept put forward by Miles and Huberman, namely data reduction, namely making an abstraction of all data obtained from all field notes as a result of interview observations and document review. b. Presentation of data. The process of presenting this data reveals the whole of a group of data obtained so that it is easy to read and understand to build a narrative. c. Conclusion and verification Data that has been patterned, focused, systematically arranged and then concluded so that the meaning of the data can be found. The conclusion is temporary and general. To obtain "grounded" conclusions, these tentative conclusions are accompanied by other new data to strengthen the conclusions made (Miles et al., 1994).

Data validity checking techniques by testing: a. Credibility by maintaining the trustworthiness of researchers in this activity, observations find characteristics and elements that are very relevant to the issue being sought and then focus on the problem in detail. Through triangulation (methods, data sources, and data collection tools) and conducting peer review through discussions. b. Transferability By carrying out detailed descriptions from data to theory, from case to case. c. Dependability, namely to maintain the consistency of this research, reviews all research activities on the data that has been obtained by paying attention to data consistency. d. Certainty (confirmability) That is trying to guarantee the reliability of the data by auditing all the data obtained to determine the certainty and quality of the data obtained.

RESEARCH RESULT

The Special Region of Yogyakarta (DIY) is the oldest region in Indonesia after East Java, which was formed by the Indonesian state government. This province-level region also has special status or special autonomy. This status is a legacy from the pre-independence era. According to the Chronicle Giyanti, Yogyakarta or Ngayogyakarta (Javanese) is the name given by Paku Buwono II (king of Mataram in 1719-1727) as a substitute for the name of the pesantren. Garjitawati. Yogyakarta means Jogja, the affluent, Yogya, which is prosperous, while Ngayogyakarta Hadiningrat means Jogja, prosperous and most important. Other sources say that the name Yogyakarta is taken from the name (mother) of the Sanskrit city of Ayodhya in the Ramayana epic. In everyday use, Yogyakarta is commonly pronounced Yogyakarta) or Ngayogyakarta (Javanese).

As the capital of the Province of the Special Region of Yogyakarta, the City of Yogyakarta is rich in titles, both originating from its history and existing potential, such as a city of struggle, a city of culture, a city of students and a city of tourism. Yogyakarta was once the centre of the kingdom, both the Mataram (Islamic) Kingdom, the Yogyakarta Sultanate and the Pakualaman Duchy. The designation of the city of culture for this city is closely related to the high-value cultural relics from the time of these kingdoms, which are still sustainable today. This term is also related to the many centres of art and culture. The term Mataram, which is widely used today, is nothing but pride for the glory of the Mataram Kingdom.

Special Region, which has an area of 3,185.80 km², consists of one municipality and four districts, which are subdivided into 78 districts and 438 villages. The Special Region of Yogyakarta is one of the 33 provinces in Indonesia and is located in the central part of the island of Java. Geographically it is located at 8° 30' - 7° 20' South Latitude and 109° 40' -111° 0' East Longitude. Ngetun Beach is a beach located in Gunung Kidul Regency, precisely in Purwodadi Village, Tepus District, Gunung Kidul, Province of the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

The condition of Ngetun Beach is seen as an accessibility factor when the research is still being conducted due to a relatively difficult lack of directions. The road to the beach is still found to be steep and potholed, so tourists must be careful in driving and controlling their vehicles. There is no special route from Yogyakarta City to Gunung Kidul Regency. To reach the location of the Ngetun Beach tourist attraction, tourists need approximately 2 hours from downtown Yogyakarta. Ngetun Beach already has several facilities, including parking facilities, eating and drinking facilities, prayer facilities, cleaning and bathroom facilities, and tent and mat rental facilities. However, the condition and quality of the existing facilities at this tourist attraction are still managed without standard operating standards, so it seems unmaintained.

Human Resources at Ngetun Beach, namely managers and coastal communities, still do not understand the advantages and benefits of this tourist attraction. So that managers and local communities do not play an active role in developing and marketing objects for this tour. The management of human resources has not been maximal in managing the Ngetun Beach tourist spot, and this has been shown by the vacuum for the past two years. However, the hospitality of the manager and the local community towards tourists is good. It can be seen from the way management and the community in responding to and serving tourists. The relationship between the manager and the local community is good, and helps each other, for example, mutual cooperation in repairing the road to the beach and keeping the environment around the beach clean.

On this beach, there is an organization that manages and that organization is responsible for the Ngetun Beach object. The organization is the Tourism Awareness Group Organization (Kelompok Sadar Wisata/Pokdarwis) which is chaired by Mr Parlan. Licensing in the management of Ngetun Beach is permission management from the government (Kelurahan Desa Purwodadi and the Wonosari Tourism Office, Gunung Kidul). However, the management is still not professional, so the handling of the beach is still traditional and is more developed for fishermen's efforts to explore their marine products. The reluctance of managers and the community to explore their area to become a tourist object is still felt. This is due to the lack of understanding of the economic value of tourism objects. There is no shared understanding of the importance of building prosperity through good management of tourist destinations apart from marine products.

Pokdarwis is still structural and functional, where a structural approach is more prominent than public participation. This approach is because the Pokdarwis manager is a regional bureaucratic administrator. So the relational relationship, relatively characteristic instructional, does not invite people to think together about how to develop the tourism

potential they have. Most Public Ngetun is still focused on the activity of becoming traditional fishermen. For those who work outside the region still do not understand the economic potential of their region as a tourist area. Besides that, there is an attitude sceptical of their tourism potential because other tourist attractions already have adequate infrastructure, which is more accessible to tourists.

The existence of beach tourism competitors not far from Ngetun Beach is a threat that can reduce or even eliminate a business's income because the products offered are the same or similar. Siung Beach is one of the threats to Ngetun Beach because Siung Beach has an international standard, namely with the annual rock climbing event. These conditions make it difficult for tourism object managers to make it the main destination for tourists to go to the beach.

The difficulty for Ngetun Beach to become one of the leading beach tourism destinations is the manager's ability to highlight a differentiator compared to other beaches. Managers still base their management on the success of Siung Beach, starting from providing beach infrastructure but not optimally, and tend to follow what Siung Beach is doing. Ngetun Beach has advantages that other beaches don't have, namely a position that is confined to a hill so that it is more exotic and has the potential for abundant fishery wealth. A beautiful sunset with a beautiful and quiet beach is the main attraction for visitors who encourage them to come to Ngetun Beach. The potential, which is quite large as capital to attract tourists, turns out to be unable to become a tourist attraction. One of them could be due to the lack of awareness by the community as a potential so that the enthusiasm of the community to continue to consistently promote their area does not occur. Community participation is still very low.

This condition is exacerbated by the absence of the government in optimal support through policies that allocate special funds for the beach that deserves to be a commodity tour. The government's vision of providing support to make the beach Ngetun a commodity superior does not exist. The government is more oriented on construction destination tours that have been present and visited by many tourists. The government is too bureaucratic when determining tourist areas based on momentary economic value. So that the beach is not given serious attention for the development of tourist destinations in the future. This can be seen in the designation of the Ngetun Beach Tourism Strategic Area (KSP) as Level III KSP, a superior tourist attraction for natural beaches with adventure tourism supporters. As Destination beach tourism supporting adventure tourism developed by the beach love the most prominent, while Ngetun beach has received less serious development attention.

DISCUSSION

Starting from the presentation of data collected through observation, in-depth interviews with research participation indicated that several aspects were not handled properly and systematically in developing coastal tourism. The lack of serious attention from the local government in developing the Ngetun Beach tourist destination has made many tourist facilities a prerequisite for tourism development not going well. Accessibility to the location

is not handled properly. Existing ecosystem location tours are not well-formed though the hang-out society is quite high, which is capital social for the development of Ngetun beach tourism. Through Potency exotic and capital tourist destinations, social society, as well as potency good seafood, will be a very high bargaining value to be marketed as a tourism product.

Coastal tourism potential, which is a bay surrounded by Shady hills with white sand, are exotic natural attractions coupled with high-value marine products such as lobsters, green mussels and other marine products, which are the basic capital to be offered internationally. This potential will be developed into a leading tourist destination if capital is invested socially for the community can be optimized by a growing shared awareness of the importance of these tourist areas as their economic source.

Pokdarwis has been responsible for raising awareness among the public to take care of and maintain objective beach tourism that still uses the structural approach. That approach still depends on structural power in mobilizing the community to be involved in tourism development. Modelinteractional is expected to be able to form a shared awareness that will encourage active community participation in coastal development efforts. Public awareness of working together in cleanliness shows the community's concern about their beach. But they do not have a high fantasy about their awareness that the beach as object tourism is able to prosper them. Even though they work together for beach infrastructure, they are not moved by awareness but by culture "Norms Manager Pokdarwis. This condition must be changed from an approach structural to an interactive communication approach.

The development of community participation in tourism development will grow if the management and development of tourism are able to provide economic, social and cultural welfare for the local community through responsible tourism. Through active participation, engagement will help prevent environmental damage caused by irresponsible tourism and can promote and reward and respect cultural diversity. Improving the role of society as a whole voluntarily in developing tourist destinations can occur through participatory communication. Participatory communication that invites the community to participate circularly by building verbal symbols of new hopes about economic benefits and welfare will encourage community participation. Model building-based tourism communities in many studies previously have implications for good tourism development.

Building community participation-based tourism through symbolic convergence communication to foster fantasy awareness interactively and not structurally will have implications for the development and continuity of tourism destinations. However, the government's role as the founder and initiator of communication development interactive and fantasy symbolization is indispensable. So as to optimize the great potential of the beach, there needs to be a government role in building potential by disbursing assistance in landscape arrangement, management and funding, as well as developing national and international events. Of course, the role of the mass media and social media will greatly help to grow people's fantasies about their promising areas. Media in the context of

marketing communications will greatly help make the beach a leading destination when the government's role and concern are high, and there is a high fantasy in the form of tourism awareness has grown.

CONCLUSION

Starting from the discussion, one can be pulled conclusion that the beach is not yet optimal sorry to become a leading destination is

1. Less than optimal government concern in developing Ngigitun Beach.
 - a) Beach regulations sorry become a priority in tourism not contained in various regional regulations that have been issued.
 - b) Funding for the procurement of infrastructure and various facilities is still very limited and partial.
 - c) Approaching a formal institution structure, which is bureaucratic, results in no flexibility manager improvise.
2. The low active participation of the community in developing the Ngigitun beach tourism area.
 - a) The formal structural approach carried out by Pokdarwis as the manager of each sorry was unable to grow collective awareness of the importance of the beach sorry.
 - b) The participation did not occur but more to the mobilization and participation of the community due to the culture of "Ewuh pakewuh, as a Javanese culture that does not want to be different from other residents."
3. There is no collective consciousness about the importance of the beach, sorry for their economic value and their welfare.
 - a) Tourism awareness groups (Pokdarwis) give more messages in a linear manner to residents.
 - b) There is no formation of an open public space to explain the importance of Ngigitun beach tourism.
 - c) Not able to optimize the existence of conventional media and new media to build fantasy together about economic value and value social culture for them.

Under beach development, sorry, to become a leading tourist, the government needs a bigger role through its publication regulation, prioritising its development. The government must pay more attention to the development of physical ecosystems for the convenience and smooth running of tourists. Pokdarwis, in building tourism awareness, should be interest-oriented travellers, not follow interaction formally with the government. The approach to communication with the community is more based on linear aperture participate. Need to build a shared fantasy about economic value and well-being together through symbolic convergence communication.

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